

FRACTURE OF THE CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES AS NON-EQUILIBRIUM KINETIC TRANSITION IN ENSEMBLE OF MICROCRACKS

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ABSTRACT

Deformation and fracture of carbon-carbon composite materials are determined by an evolution of ensemble of microscopic defects. A multiscale character of the quasi-brittle fracture is displayed as simultaneous development of the qualitatively different defects (microcracks, their localization pileups, macroscopic discontinuities). A statistic approach allowed a system of macroscopic constitutive equations to be obtained. It allows to describe kinetics of damage accumulation in two interacting subsystems: matrix and fibres. Topological aspects of quasi-brittle fracture are examined with the use of the fractal theory.

Keywords: microcracks ensemble, quasi-brittle fracture, non-linear kinetic transitions, dissipative structure, topological transitions, fractals.

1. STATISTICAL DESCRIPTION AND CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS OF THE CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

1.1. Interacting microcracks statistic.

A number of unique properties inherent to the carbon materials make them indispensable for production of new composites which could be used in processes, involving the extreme temperature and loading rate parameters. However, these materials exhibit some specific characteristics that are not typical for traditional materials. A relatively high strength of the latter is associated with the marked ability to relax due to the local plasticity in the vicinity of incipient defects. This mechanism is actually not apparent in the carbon-carbon materials and the main reason for relaxation is a nucleation and growth of new structural defects. In the fracture analysis of a carbon-carbon composite materials the emphasis should be placed on the two main aspects of the problem: the presence of the volume microcrack accumulation and the well-defined statistical character of fracture. Referring to the main aspects of the statistical description, developed in [1,2], the function of the microcrack distribution takes the form

$$W(s, \vec{v}) = Z^{-1} \exp(-E/Q), \quad (1)$$

where $E = -H_{ik}s_{ik} + \alpha s_{ik}^2$ is the energy of microcracks, the volume s and orientation \vec{v} of which are determined by the tensor s_{ik} ; $H_{ik} = \gamma\sigma_{ik} + \lambda p_{ik}$ is the effective force field, imposed on the microcrack by the external (macroscopic) stresses σ_{ik} and surrounding microcracks with the force proportional to tensor of microcrack density $p_{ik} = n\langle s_{ik} \rangle$. Here n is the microcrack concentration; λ, α, γ and Q are calibrating parameters, defining the initial structure; Z is normalizing parameter. The averaging of s_{ik} with the distribution function $W(s_{ik})$

$$p_{ik} = n \int s_{ik} Z^{-1} \exp(-E/Q) ds d^3\vec{v} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. The dependence of defect density p on stress σ : oa - thermodynamic branch, ac - unstable branch.

over the material parameter range, corresponding to the pronounced (large scale) structural heterogeneity and representing the strong defect interaction (defined by the values of dimensionless parameter $\delta = 2\alpha / \lambda, /3/$) yields a non-linear dependence of p_{ik} on the applied stress (Figure 1). The dependence involves the region of metastability oa and absolute instability ac .

1.2. Non-linear damage kinetics in composite materials

An initial stage of the damage process is characterized by the rupture of individual fibres, their spallation from the matrix and microcrack development in the matrix. However, the fibre failure is preceded by the damage accumulation at the microstructure level. The majority of approaches ignores these effects, though it is generally agreed among researchers that the evolution of microscopic imperfections leads to the fibre softening the strength of their linked with the matrix. Fracture modelling of carbon composites at different structural levels requires an adequate physical explanation of the fracture mechanism, a deep understanding of statistical aspects of transition from the elementary damage mode (initiation and growth of microcracks) to macroscopic failure and derivation of state equations which describe reasonably well the evolution of structural defects, taking account of characteristic scale of structural heterogeneity. From the analysis of microcrack system as the statistical ensemble it is readily seen that the transition from disperse to macroscopic

fracture takes place under conditions of non-equilibrium (kinetic) transition, when drastic microcracks growth is governed by non-linear character of microcrack interaction /3/.

While modelling deformation behaviour and fracture of carbon composites is convenient to start with an expression for the volume concentration of free energy F , reflected the results of statistical description. This expression should include terms describing elastic strain of the composite u_{ik} and contribution to the free energy, introduced by matrix and fibre microcrack opening under corresponding stresses σ_{ik}^m and σ_{ik}^f :

$$F = G_{iklm} u_{ik} u_{lm} / 2 + V_m F_m(\sigma_{ik}^m, p_{ik}^m) + V_f F_f(\sigma_{ik}^f, p_{ik}^f). \quad (3)$$

Here G_{iklm} is the elastic module tensor of the composite; V_m and V_f are the volume fractions of matrix and fibres; σ_{ik}^m , σ_{ik}^f , p_{ik}^m and p_{ik}^f are the stresses and measures of damage in the matrix and fibres respectively. Let consider the generation and growth of microcracks to be main cause of the energy dissipation in carbon composites, then the evolution relation can be written as /1/

$$\frac{\delta F}{\delta t} = V_f \frac{\delta F^f}{\delta p_{ik}^f} \dot{p}_{ik}^f + V_m \frac{\delta F^m}{\delta p_{ik}^m} \dot{p}_{ik}^m \leq 0. \quad (4)$$

To satisfy the fixed sign condition (Equation 4) the relationship between generalized flows and forces may be represented in a form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p}_{ik}^f &= -\alpha_1 V_f \frac{\delta F^f}{\delta p_{ik}^f} - \alpha_2 V_m \frac{\delta F^m}{\delta p_{ik}^m}, \\ \dot{p}_{ik}^m &= -\alpha_2 V_f \frac{\delta F^f}{\delta p_{ik}^f} - \alpha_3 V_m \frac{\delta F^m}{\delta p_{ik}^m}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where kinetic coefficients α_i satisfy the following inequalities: $\alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 > 0, \alpha_1 \alpha_2 > \alpha_2^2$. Equations 5 demonstrate the essential influence of the component volume concentration on the fracture kinetics. By renormalization of the kinetic coefficients α_i , the volume concentrations V_f and V_m actually affect characteristic times of fracture in matrix and fibres. For fibres, having a considerable higher elastic modules over that of matrix, it is evident that $\frac{\delta F^f}{\delta p_{ik}^f} > \frac{\delta F^m}{\delta p_{ik}^m}$. This explains the

fact that the fibre damage prevails at the initial stage of fracture in composites reinforced with carbon fibres. In the following, depending on the fibre concentration V_f , the fibre damage of composites may either localize or initiate a complete failure of material. In the former case there occurs a gradual damage of fibres and essential strengthening of crushed fibres. This phenomenon is characteristic of carbon-carbon composites with low volume fraction of fibres. When loading composites with a high volume fraction of fibres even the first fibre ruptures cause the material to collapse so that the high statistic mean of fibres is not realised.

The macroscopic parameter which characterizes the damage of the unit volume of composite can be written in the form $p_{ik} = V_f p_{ik}^f + V_m p_{ik}^m$. The expression for free energy F reflected the results of statistical description was used in the form of Landau expansion /4/

$$F = A p_{ik}^2 + B p_{ik}^3 + C p_{ik}^4 - D \sigma_{ik} p_{ik}, \quad (6)$$

where A, B, C and D are phenomenological materials parameters.

The continuum problem of quasi-brittle fracture includes the equations of motion

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ik}}{\partial x_k}, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial p_{ik}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{\tau_p} \frac{\partial F}{\partial p_{ik}} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\chi \frac{\partial p_{ik}}{\partial x_l} \right), \quad (8)$$

constitutive equations of elastic medium with microcracks

$$u_{ik} = c_{iklm} \sigma_{lm} + \mathcal{Y}_{ik}, \quad (9)$$

plus the boundary and initial conditions /1/.

Here u_i, u_{ik}, c_{iklm} are correspondingly the vector of displacements, the strain tensor and elastic ductility tensor. The material parameters were defined by the directly experiments for carbon-carbon composites. In following the parameter of nonlocality χ is taken to be zero, which corresponds to assumption that the characteristic time of the microcrack growth τ_p is the essentially higher than that of nonhomogeneity revealed in the distribution of stresses by the nonhomogeneous field p . The analysis of the behaviour of eigenforms for the equation of the motion of parameter p_{ik} at $\chi=0$ demonstrates that their associated of localization scales are increasingly growing in size l . The fracture mechanism involves the increased growth of existing microcracks or nucleation of new ones as a result of the elastic energy release due to a collapse of a microvolume. The release of elastic energy has an acceleration effect on the development of microdamage process in the nearest neighbourhood so as the scale of microdamage increases with the growth of elastic strain energy and decrease of dissipative energy of the material. These two peculiarities are clearly manifested in fracture of carbon materials.

Figure 2. The strength distribution function $F_{\sigma}(\sigma)$ of the carbon- carbon composites.

The experiments on tensile test specimens made of carbon-carbon composite reveal characteristic features of deformation and fracture: the presence of microcracks in the bulk of the specimen; the influence of cracking on the deformation behaviour of materials; fragmentation of the specimen across the regions subject to damage and highly statistical scattering of specimen strength. The results of experimental study are presented in Figure 2. The empirical function of the specimens strength distribution corresponded to a two parameter (Weibull) distribution. The peculiarities of damage promoted the employment of the computer numerical simulation for prediction of deformation behaviour and fracture. The method involves solution of the boundary problem of quasi-brittle fracture including the non-linear kinetic equation for parameter p_{ik} . The constants of this equation were random quantities from experimentally obtained intervals for every element of finite-element approximation.

2. KINETIC TRANSITIONS AND TOPOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FRACTURE

2.1. Self-organization phenomena in ensembles of microcracks

The motion equation for parameter p_k (Equation 8) describes a number of significant qualitative effects characteristic of quasi-brittle fracture. In the range of stresses and initial values of p_{ik} , corresponding to a thermodynamical branch oa (Figure 1), the level of damage is controlled by the

magnitude of the applied stresses, where as beyond this limit ($\sigma > \sigma_c$ or $p(t=0) > p_c$) the behaviour of elastic medium with defects may differ from case due to nonlinearity of its properties. Characteristic features of such system evolution are associated with the group properties of nonlinear operator (Equation 8), which in turn define the eigenfunction spectrum of the nonlinear problem under consideration. These eigenfunctions correspond to the self-similarity solutions of the Equation 8 at the developed stage of the system behaviour and define for a particular form of nonlinearity the spectrum of spatial-time forms of solutions (dissipative structures of various complexity /5/).

In /6/ was shown to have several types of self-similar solution, which, as applied to the problems of damage accumulation, correspond to a localized infinite growth of p_k over a range of constant or "growing" space scales. This situation are typical for deformable medium in case of initiation of stabilizing or extending fracture centres. The evolution of dissipative structure for the Equation 8 is described by the self-similarity solution /6/ :

$$p(\bar{x}, t) = g(t)f(\xi), \quad \bar{\xi} = \bar{x} / \varphi(t), \quad (10)$$

where $g(t)$ govern the growth law for the amplitude of the defect density parameter p and $\varphi(t)$ defines variations over the half-width of localization region. From Equation 10 follow that the time distribution of p remains self-similar: it simply extends by a certain factor along the x and p -axes. Substitution Equation 10 into the Equation 8 allows to clarify the form of the function $g(t)$

$$g(t) = G(1 - t/t_c)^{-m}, \quad (11)$$

where $G > 0, m > 0$ are the parameters of nonlinearity, which characterize the rate of "power" reduction of the free energy level $\frac{\partial F}{\partial p}$ with the increase of the volume microcrack concentration in the region $p > p_c (\sigma > \sigma_c)$, (Figure 1). Concurrently the eigenvalue problem is formulated for the eigenfunction $f(\xi)$. Its solution gives the spectrum of eigenforms $f_i(\xi)$ "living" in the discrete range of eigenvalues ξ_i , specifying the localization scales. The solution (Equation 10) refers to the class of nonlinear singular solutions, describing an infinite growth of $p(t)$ over localization scale at $t \rightarrow t_c$.

2.2. Topological transitions in microcrack ensemble and regularities of the carbon-carbon composites fracture

The spectrum of localization scales (infinite in a general case) and the associated time rate of defect evolution specify the characteristic size and time of transition to a qualitatively new type of defect (from microcracks to the centres of macroscopic fracture). In this case the possibility of analyzing the system behaviour in the context of continuum formulation proves to be the matter of considerable importance.

The solid with multiple interacting cracks is proposed to be dissipative system capable to alter the character of its behaviour from the regular to a random one at small variations of certain parameters. The reason of this phenomena is a local instability over the stability threshold of thermodynamical branch. Local instability induces significant transformation of the dissipative system, accompanied by alteration of its topological properties. It is a well-established fact that stochasticity, caused by the local instability, is fractal by its nature /7/.

With the available invariant-group solutions to the Equation 8, localized in the spectrum of spatial scales, one may give quite natural interpretation for the fractal regularities of fracture, based on the similarity considerations /8,9/. The concept of fractals was originally introduced by Mandelbrot /10/ for a set, dimension of which is strictly larger then topological one $d_H > d_T$:

$$d_H = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \frac{\ln N(r)}{\ln(1/r)}, \quad (12)$$

where r is characteristic dimension of cubes, filling the phase volume, $N(r)$ is a number of cubes, enclosing at least one element the of the set. The dimension d_H introduced in this way allows to differentiate the extent of complexity and intricacy of trajectories and, actually, represents the principle of scale invariance of the considered set.

The problem of quasi-brittle fracture of the carbon-carbon composite plate has been solved numerically based on Equations 7-9. The simulation of the specimen involves a macroscopic defect has readily demonstrated that under loading the initial stage is accompanied by preferential failure of element located in the vicinity of the macroscopic defect with damage accumulation according simultaneously in the rest of the plate. The percolation cluster across the specimen results from coalescence of the cluster originated from the initial macrodefect and clusters in its immediate neighbourhood. The cluster appears to be fractal by character and with increase of linear dimension L its mass increases on the average as:

$$M(L) = AL^D, \tag{13}$$

where D is the fractal dimension, A is the effective amplitude.

Numerical prediction for topological properties of the cluster being the generated in the vicinity of the initial macrodefect are presented in the Figure 3 as the logarithmic dependence of the cluster mass M (i.e. the number of failed elements) on the side length of the initial "cell" L enclosing the cluster $||1||$. The dependence $M(L)$ is seen to consist of two linear portions (Figure 3), the slope of which is determined by the fractal dimension D . The cluster growth characterized by the fractal dimension $D = 1$ is predominantly normal to the loading direction. The growth of the clusters not associated with the defect leads to the increased value of the fractal dimension D , which may be as high as 1.4-1.7. This is indicative of qualitative changes in the topology of damage accumulation process and the fracture mechanism replacement.

Figure 3. Dependence of cluster mass M on characteristic dimension L .

The measure of fractal dimension $D = 1$ supports the validity of the approaches of linear fracture mechanics only at initial stage of crack evolution, when the crack propagation is defined by disturbance of the stress fields in the vicinity of the crack. However, this holds true for sufficiently large crack when the extension of the distributed stress region d is essentially lower than crack length

$l(d/l \ll 1)$. In general case when the initial microcrack size is below some critical value $l < l_c$ the process of fracture evolution lacks "the intermediate-asymptotic mode" [8] by crack propagation. This significantly contributes to the understanding of the fact, that linear fracture mechanics generalizations to be used as the basis for describing fracture stage can be not justified for each case. The evidence for this is the increase of the fractal dimension up to value $D > 1$, both in the presence of the initial microcrack with $l > l_c$ and at $l < l_c$.

In Figure 4 the results of statistical simulation for the times of complete formation of the main cluster are plotted as "the number of the failed elements N in the initial macrodefect" VS "critical concentration of the failed elements at the time of the main cluster formation X ". This dependence involves two parts. The former corresponds to the formation of the branched cluster with the fractal dimension $D = 1$. The transient region between these portions defines the critical size N_a^c of the initial defect, which specifies two qualitatively different mechanisms of material fracture according to the size of initial defects. The latter are always available in actual materials, suggesting that the highest reliability of materials is reached when the size of initial defects is not more than N_a^c . In this case the material exhibits the highest "dissipative capacity" and accumulation of defects in the bulk of the specimen will be more homogeneous.

Figure 4: Variation of critical concentration of the failed regions X_C with dimension of initial macrodefect N_a .

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